

Serious Game with emphasis on Global Prosperity: developing the Game Reis Magos from Design Science

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Abstract

Serious Games increasingly receive the support and interest from teachers as another active teaching methodology that, built to achieve educational goals, also manages to motivate and attract the attention of students. The objective of the research is to describe the development of a serious game used to assist in the teaching-learning process of global prosperity. To this end, qualitative research was performed, adopting the Design Science model. As for the results, it was identified that constant testing added value to the construction of the game. Another contribution of the study is the emphasis on the concern that developers or educators must have regarding some elements in games, such as the rules and mechanics. The research brought contributions to the educational process, as well as business practice, with the combination of teaching cases and educational games.

Keywords: Case Method. Global Prosperity. Design Science.

1 Introduction

The social and technological context and new contemporary social habits and practices, in addition to the generation of digital natives (Prensky, 2003) who have an innate ability to learn how to interact online (McGonigal, 2011) trigger the growing emergence of new approaches and educational possibilities, allowing the expansion of pedagogical actions in the classroom (Figueiredo, et al., 2015).

From this perspective, active learning methodologies, such as case studies and serious games, have several advantages: allowing for the establishment of links between the teaching environment and the real world; leading students to the variability of solutions; favouring the establishment of relationships between variables; contributing to the analysis of a problem from different points of view; requiring students to publicly express their ideas and subject them to criticism; adjusting to different levels of teaching complexity, and they can also be used both in face-to-face and distance learning (Alves et al., 2015; Bacich & Moran, 2018).

As an active learning methodology, Teaching Cases are commonly used as a complement to other teaching methods, usually based on the deductive method of teaching-learning, thus, they are based on theories, models, or concepts (Roesch, 2007).

For Alves et al. (2015), Gamification is an active teaching methodology that arises, in this sense, with the principle of appropriation of elements used in games for contexts of products and services not focused on games, but to promote engagement and learning. Unlike games, the goal of gamification is not just having fun, hence serious games.

The gamification process analyzed here had the pedagogical purpose of teaching and making students aware of the concept of Global Prosperity. This concept has emerged in recent decades questioning the centrality of economic growth as a measure of success and well-being of a community, proposing a multifaceted analysis that considers alternative and contextualized values to judge the quality of life of a society.

Since its establishment, the concept of Sustainable Development, and initiatives derived from it, have become the target of criticism, either for the false symmetry between the three factors propagated (Flint, 2010; Paes,

2017), for the impossibility of reconciling an ecologically viable economy with the objectives of a capitalist system (Vizeu, et al., 2012), or by the contradictions of equalizing “growth” with the obvious limitations of resources (Misoczky & Böhm 2012).

In this context, the concept of Global Prosperity emerges as a critical alternative to the unifying perspective of Sustainable Development, focused on growth. Thus, the concept is particularly averse to the vision of prosperity in a community defined by the notion of economic wealth (Sender et al, 2020).

In this way, the research aims to describe the development of a serious game to assist in teaching-learning Global Prosperity from tests with Design Science. To achieve this objective, the following specific objectives were defined: presenting the process of game building; - presenting the adjustments in the game structure; - describing the structural elements of the game; - describing the game.

1.1 Theoretical elements

To understand the theoretical elements that would be part of the game, the researchers focused on comprehending the design that a game should have, and for that, they were based on the Theory of Flow, and also, to achieve educational goals, the Theory of Global Prosperity was deepened, bringing to the game a reflexive character about the complex reality surrounding the player.

Kirriemuir and McFarlene (2004) comment that several researchers and video game developers based their investigations on the theory of flow (figure 1), that shows that the shape or state of the flow depends on a combination of challenges and skills.

Figure 1. Theory of flow source: Csikszentmihalyi, 1990.

For a person to reach a state of flow or challenge, they must report to the level of their own difficulties. For example, in a situation (A1), the person is still learning to play with only a few skills at that time, or with reduced challenge levels, so the degree of difficulty is suited to their skill (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990).

At this point, we are in a flow situation, which is likely to be short-lived, as the player will improve their dexterity by repeating and adapting to the flow of the game. If no level changes occur in the challenge (A2), the player will start to feel bored and presumably give up on the task. If the challenges are too far above the obstacles, it will cause anxiety (A3), which can also lead to abandoning the game.

Lopes and Oliveira (2013) state that for a flow situation to occur, a continuous balance is needed between the challenges presented and the current capabilities of the player ($A1 > A4$).

From a game-components perspective, Busarello (2016) highlights that gamification values five structural elements: 1) learning; 2) game mechanics; 3) in-game thinking; 4) motivation and engagement; 5) narrative.

Vianna et al. (2013) and Zichermann and Cunningham (2011) point out that, to keep the student motivated in the game building process, it is necessary to appropriate its most efficient elements - mechanics, dynamic and aesthetic. The first comprises the elements of the functioning of the game, that guide the player in their actions; while the second are the moments of interaction between the player and these mechanics; and, finally, the aesthetic refers to the emotions of the players in the moments of interaction with the game, also reflecting the previous relationships with mechanics and dynamics.

Hanus and Fox (2015) emphasize that one must be careful when defining rewards throughout the game, because certain extrinsic rewards can destroy intrinsic motivations, affecting the motivational aspect of the individual.

In this way, for the proposed game, a theory that contemplated a model extrapolating the 'economicist' metrics was designed. Sustainability sees growth, in an economic sense, as necessary, especially with regard to solving poverty and misery, emphasizing metrics such as GDP and family income.

In this sense, the concept of Global Prosperity promotes a multifaceted vision capable of seeing beyond the economic dimension, incorporating values, quality of life, and well-being in its analysis, given a specific context (Moore, 2015). For a real Prosperity to be sustainable, it must combine the development of the ability to live well on a planet with finite resources, with the quality of life and relationships, the resilience of communities, and a sense of collective and individual meaning (Jackson, 2017).

Thus, Global Prosperity envisages rethinking global society and its priorities, reframing much of what is thought about life in the global south. Although historically classified as "developing" or "underdeveloped", the rupture of a uniform vision of what prosperity means, and the end of a linear and evolutionary developmental vision, makes it possible to focus on what quality of life actually means for a given community.

Many experiments have been performed in the development of Prosperity analysis tools (Sender et al., 2020). In this sense, the Legatum Institute created a ranking of Global Prosperity among countries, analysing the variables security, economic quality, governance, business environment, individual freedoms, social capital, education, health, and environment (Legatum Institute, 2020).

Moore (2015), while recognizing the merit of the UN Sustainable Development Goals in establishing standards and timelines for implementation, points to the need for more goals to be created considering the necessary diversity and contextualization of Global Prosperity, which calls for a change in the concept of wealth, values and social progress.

Thus, we have sought to assemble the elements of gamification for the educational purpose of generating skills necessary to understand the complexity of decisions in a teaching-learning context that thinks of Global Prosperity. Lopes and Oliveira (2013) and Alves (et al., 2015) define this type of gamification as serious game.

2 Methodology

This research is of the Design Science type. This term highlights the orientation, which goes from the development of knowledge to the design of solutions for real-world problems, and the tools necessary to perform appropriate actions attributable to professionals. In this case, a game that helps the teacher, in a management context in higher education, to develop specific skills in their students, in particular the ability of superior thinking based on the reflection of multiple decision-making possibilities.

Sordi, Meireles, and Sanches (2010) state that the process of using knowledge to plan and create an artifact, when it is carefully, systematically, and rigorously analyzed about the effectiveness with which it achieves its goal, can be called Design Science and applied in research in Administration.

In the present case, the game developed from this research is characterized as an artifact systematically developed from an iterative process of constant validation. Venable (2006) proposes a framework for the procedures of Design Science research, shown in figure 2

Figure 2. Framework for the Design Science research. Source: Venable (2006).

In figure 2, problem and solution are placed in the same flow, where it is possible to confront them to propose new theories or hypotheses. Although the activities can be developed without a theoretical definition, during the progress of the building-development-validation process, the theoretical construction occurs when analyzing the interactions to understand the problem, its causes, and consequences; when defining and testing the artifact and; with the validation of the results obtained by its application.

Based on figure 2, by Venable (2006), we can divide the research into 3 phases: building, natural or artificial evaluation, and development. It is important to highlight the circular model of the system, a beneficial feature in model validation.

The building stage seeks to understand how it is done, how it should be done, and the success parameters that are adopted in the literature. For this, the basis of the work is theoretical, making the test versions of the game into conceptual work frameworks, trying to create a solid base in which the educational principles of the game were fostered.

Based on this, there are changes made from an evaluation; whether artificial from a role-playing simulation or even simulations from action research, when researchers are involved in adaptation meetings; or even, field studies, as in tests with subjects brought from outside the research.

The results of this iterative model, even if partial in this process, already denote a "design research", while the result of this type of research can be either the finished artifact or an improvement in an artifact that exists, or is in development.

2.1 Serious game Reis Magos

The game Reis Magos was inspired by the teaching case Reis Magos Hotel. It portrays a decision-making situation involving a manager, regarding the fate of an important landmark for tourism, in addition to being a historical and cultural monument in the city of Natal, in Rio Grande do Norte.

Throughout the case, data demonstrating the golden years of the Hotel are shown, followed by changes in the places, due to the expansion of tourism to other regions of the city, and the consequent period of decay of the hotel.

In the teaching case, the student is in the position of the manager, owner of the establishment, and is faced with quantitative and qualitative data related to historical, cultural, economic, and social issues surrounding the hotel, as well as possible choices.

From these reflections and ideas, there was an interest in the use of gamification. This originated discussions regarding its applications, bringing important regional and cultural aspects, and a complex vision of a phenomenon commonly analyzed and decided in favour of profitability and efficiency at any cost, including in the actual outcome of the case in question.

2.2 Structuring of the artifact.

According to the method for the construction of a Design Research, explained by Venable (2006), the three revision phases must occur circularly until the artifact requirements are reached.

The building phase, with the insertion of some authors of more current methodology and references, was basically conducted during the preparation of the Teaching Case and also in the review of the concepts for the construction of the reference, detailed in the session of the Theoretical Elements of this work.

Having partially overcome the building phase, given its restriction of format, the evaluation and development phases started. To facilitate the organization of this phase, it was divided into three equivalent fronts, implemented during developer meetings based on design thinking: ideation, prototyping, and testing, that is, every meeting occurred iteratively in the construction of what the game would be.

It is important to emphasize that the entire evaluation and development process happened in the context of the pandemic. Thus, all steps were performed in weekly meetings at distance with the support of online software as Google Meet.

Regarding ideation, it can be considered a natural assessment, as the researchers were immersed in the process of developing ideas that would contribute to the construction of an initial prototype.

The requirements adopted in the ideation phase were that the game should supply the need to continue the Teaching Case; have at least 3 activities, an interactive one, a collaborative one, and a reflexive one, that led to pondering about the implications of their actions in the game; it should provide conditions for students to develop skills for complex thinking from the theory of global prosperity; and have a graphic representation that alludes to the elements of the Teaching Case (the Hotel and the City).

The part of the meeting that included prototyping can also be considered a natural assessment, since the developers were creating, modifying, or even improving the result of the ideation phase, in the form of the operationalization of rules, mechanics, and educational objectives.

In the testing phases, there were two types of experiments:

Internal tests, which took place periodically, with the developers themselves. A member would always act as a tutor, conducting the activity, due to changes in rules and new mechanics. This role was fundamental, mainly at the beginning.

External testing was on-demand, as soon as we had a first viable prototype that met the requirements. Due to social distancing, we have performed it at the student residence where one of the researchers lived. Other researchers observed this test by video conference software. Both types of testing can be considered artificial evaluations. One of role-playing (internal), and a field study (external).

The main contributions of artificial evaluations were given in 3 dimensions: Game Communication, Mechanics, Resource Balance.

Regarding game communication, contributions to initial information on the map helped in the preliminary communication for those who did not yet know the main rules of the game. As well as the inclusion of the location of the Hotel helped players to create reference and empathy with the city and its culture. The standardization of nomenclatures, such as "turns", "acts", and "resources".

As for the mechanics, the inclusion of more interactive parts, such as the exchange mechanics were important in two points: in the creation of a collaborative environment and the balance of points, when in an environment

conducive to these exchanges, whether due to the scarcity or abundance of a resource. Another contribution to the mechanics was the inclusion of luck or bad luck.

In the balance of features, the main factor that led to this fundamental part of the game design was the repetition of internal tests. The importance of repetition in identifying biases concerning resource imbalances was easily identified when viewing the annotations made in the tests.

This way, we need to understand what the structural elements that the game implemented in its development were, and then move on to their description.

3 Describing the structural elements of the game

Prior, the developers intended to make the game as interactive as possible, thus, characteristics common to Role Play Games (RPG) were used, where the player assumes the role of a character, which has its own history, characteristics, and motivations.

In this way, the game presents the narrative of the characters through three cards distributed throughout the gameplay, they contain a description of motivations and objectives, from the characters, about what should be done with the Hotel. This is also the first contact with the character. This aims to convey a point of view, where the player can identify or not with the motivations, generating or not an empathetic link with the character.

As the game progresses, the player receives information about what happened to the Hotel, from its construction to the most current moment in the case, along with other points of view on what should be done with the organization. This qualitative information ends up influencing the decisions of the winner, as in that moment the player can use the information along with their persuasion skills to defend the point of view from their character, winning the game or not.

During the internal validations, the developers noticed that the main moments where the motivation was highest were at the beginning of each act, when players receive a new card related to their character, delving deeper into their narrative and, with it, they received a letter presenting the historic moment of the Hotel, generating a broad vision of the period in which they are inserted.

In addition to the beginning of the acts, the end of the game also represents a peak of motivation, as the strategy chosen by the player is put to the test and everything, they learned during the game can be used as an argument in his defence in defining the winner.

As this is based on a true story, the demands for resources vary a lot between the possible decisions of what will be done with the Hotel, so the researchers have chosen to divide them into 4 types, to measure the objectives within the game, namely:

1. Monetary Resources: they represent how resources related to money or goods are needed for players to reach their individual goals;
2. Social Resources: they represent how much of the social demand must be met for players to reach their individual goals;
3. Media resources: they represent how many media-related activities players need to reach their goal;
4. Political resources: they represent how much political influence players need to achieve their goal.

These features are directly linked to the individual goals and narratives of each character, being part of one of the main factors of gamification, which is the transformation of actions or events into resources, and thus motivating players to seek the most demanded resources to achieve their goals. Finally, diversifying strategies from each of them according to their demands.

3.1 Introducing the Reis Magos

The game starts with the delivery of the character sheet (figure 3), in this image we can see, in the upper left corner, the individual goals of the character, each one represented by a symbol. From top to bottom: monetary resource, social resource, political, and media resource.

The name of the character is right above its image, and, in the text, part of the story is narrated, which will have a close relationship with the established goals. During the game, the resources acquired by each player must be counted individually, for this it is recommended to use a notepad to manage them.

To prepare the cards, the developers used some popular board games as a model. Pandemic and Monopoly were the main examples; thus, the cards are also one of the attractive aspects of the game. The software's used was Microsoft word, PowerPoint and Excel to organize the texts and the cards design.

Figure 3. Businessperson card. Source: Venable (2006).

As inspiration for the design of the map, the researchers chose the game map from The Godfather board Game, where each region has its resources and characteristics, in this way each area has its peculiarities and, with this, players must create their strategies considering these factors.

At first, the researchers chose the regions closest to the Hotel location to be present in the game, however, during the development stage, demands from the group emerged so that all regions of Natal were present on the map, aiming to represent less privileged regions of the city (figure 4).

At the beginning of the game, only areas 1 and 2 were available for players to select, each one has the number of moves relative to the number of players, i.e., 3 players 3 moves. The move consists of selecting one of the empty circles and placing your piece in it, receiving the resources available there. The number of vacancies in each area is the same as the number of players.

Figure 4. Map of the game.

The game has 4 types of cards, they are used to distribute resources, give bonuses or penalties, while they are also the main narration device of the case.

The resource cards (figure 5) have some resources and tell a little about the history of the Hotel, this information is read to all players and can be used as an argument for defining the winner:

Figure 5. Resource card.

In addition to the businessperson cards (figure 3), presented at the beginning of the game description, there are Act cards (figure 6), which report the historical period in which the game takes place, representing the time of the game advancing.

Figure 6. Act cards.

Finally, there are the luck or bad luck cards (figure 7) aimed at randomly giving bonuses or penalizing players.

Figure 7. Luck and bad luck cards.

There are game moments to help players achieve the goals from their characters, at the beginning and end of the third act when players can make cards exchanges. As the resources are part of the cards, when an exchange occurs, the previous resource is lost and the new one is received.

The winner of the game is decided in three moments, the first is the strategic evaluation, where each player presents their cards and checks whether they reached their individual goal. After that, each player who did it must defend, in a coherent way, dialoguing with the information he obtained during the game, the reasons why his character deserves the victory, and which benefits will be brought both to the Hotel region and the city of Natal.

Following the presentations, all players must vote to define the winner. If the result is not yet determined, an external person (the teacher, tutor, or a person chosen by the players) must hear the defences presented and decide the outcome.

After the winner is announced, everyone should read the epilogue cards (figures 8 and 9) related to the character, keeping in mind that each card has a prerequisite written on it. After this, a joint reflection should be made as to whether this was the best option for the future of both the Hotel and the city of Natal. This moment serves to develop a critical view of the social issues that are inherent to the Hotel case.

Figure 8. Epilogue cards 1 and 2.

Figure 9. Epilogue card 3.

4 Conclusion

We believe that the objective of this research, which was to describe the development of a serious game to assist in the teaching-learning of global prosperity from tests with Design Science, was achieved. We could see that with Design Science methodology, constant modifications and tests were performed, enhancing the construction of the game and providing changes that have improved its overall quality.

Another contribution of the study is highlighting the concern that developers or educators should have about game elements during development: Communication of game elements, Mechanics, Balance of Resources.

We believe that research is relevant both for theory and the educational process, as well as for business practice. This is demonstrated in the possibility of building games from teaching cases, thus contributing to the development of people through the dissemination and adoption of the combination of these two methodological teaching strategies.

We recognize that the study had limitations. Despite the game being built, it was not tested with a large sample, only remotely, due to the pandemic. In this sense, we suggest further testing performed by studies with large samples, in quantitative research, and, in addition, new research conducted in person.

5 Final considerations

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6 References

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